

Insecticide-treated plots yielded 8.75 t/ha, untreated check plots 3.41 t/ha. *h*

Effect of spacing on leaf folder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée infestation in rice

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We studied the effect of spacing on leaf folder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée infestation in rice during January-March 1982. Variety TNAU 17005 was field tested at Paddy Breeding Station, Coimbatore, India.

Four spacings were evaluated in six replications. Nitrogen fertilizer was applied as urea supergranules at 75 kg N/ha, P and K each were applied at 40 kg/ha. Differential leaf folder infestation was recorded 55 days after transplanting. Total leaves and total leaves infested by larvae were counted on 10 randomly selected hills in each plot (see table).

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Spacing (cm)	Infestation (%)
10 × 15	36
15 × 20	26
22.5 × 20	7
30 × 20	12

Mean infestation in the plots ranged from 7 to 36%. Plants with close spacing (10 × 15 cm) recorded significantly higher infestation than plants spaced 22.5 × 20 cm and 30 × 20 cm. *h*

Pest management and control WEEDS

Efficiency of some herbicides and hand weeding for transplanted rice weed control

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Field experiments during the 1980 wet season at Palli Siksha Sadana, Visva-Bharati University, Sriniketan, tested new herbicides and herbicide combinations for their ability to suppress weeds

in transplanted rice. *Echinochloa colonum*, *Echinochloa crus-galli* (grasses), and *Ludwigia parviflora* (broadleaf) were predominant weeds in the field.

Oxyfluorfen EC effectively controlled grasses, broadleaf weeds, and sedges when applied at 0.096, 0.120, and 0.144 kg ai/ha 4 days after transplanting (DT) (see table). However, rice plants yellowed after application, and although they recovered after 2-3 weeks, crop yields were reduced.

Fluchloralin EC (0.720 ai/ha, applied 2 days before transplanting [DBV]) followed by bentazon (0.960 kg ai/ha 25 DT) produced highest grain and straw yield. Hand weeding or rotary weeding 25 and 45 DT produced similar results.

Incorporating fluchloralin EC (0.960 kg ai/ha) at puddling, 2 DBT, produced the next best yield. When no weeding was done, 39% grain yield loss was observed, compared to the best treatment. *h*

Effect of herbicides and hand weeding on weed weight and rice yield, West Bengal, India.^a

Herbicide, weeding	Application		Weed dry wt (g/m ²) 50 DT	Grain yield (t/ha)
	kg ai/ha	Time		
Oxyfluorfen EC	0.096	4 DT	12.6	2.7
Oxyfluorfen EC	0.120	4 DT	12.5	2.6
Oxyfluorfen EC	0.144	4 DT	11.8	2.9
Fluchloralin EC	0.720	2 DBT	12.9	3.3
Fluchloralin EC	0.960	2 DBT	6.0	4.0
Bentazon AS	0.960	25 DT	23.9	3.1
Bentazon AS	1.440	25 DT	20.5	3.1
Fluchloralin G - 2,4-D IPE	0.500		12.8	3.6
Fluchloralin G - 2,4-D EE	0.500			
	0.625	2 DT	12.6	3.6
Fluchloralin EC fb bentazon AS	0.720	2 DBT		
	0.960	25 DT	5.8	4.1
Fluchloralin G fb bentazon AS	0.675	2 DBT		
	0.960	25 DT	3.0	4.1
Hand weeding		25 & 45 DT	5.1	4.1
Rotary weeding		25 & 45 DT	5.2	4.0
Unweeded control			48.6	2.5
SEm ±			2.7	0.6
C.D. at 5%			8.4	1.8
CV			6%	3%

^aDT = days after transplanting, DBT = days before transplanting, G = granular, EC = emulsifiable concentrate, AS = aqueous solution, fb = followed by.

Chemical weed control in dryland rice

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In 1976-78 three chemical herbicides were evaluated for control of common weeds in dryland rice fields of eastern Uttar Pradesh. Two concentrations of active ingredient of each herbicide were compared with hand weeding and no weeding. Test plots were 5 × 2.5 m. The experimental layout was a randomized block design with treatments replicated 4 times.

Variety Narendra (IET2232) was sown at 100 kg seed/ha in rows 20 cm apart using a wheelhoe. Nutrients were applied at 60-30-30 kg NPK/ha. Half